

A MODEL FOR DEVELOPING STUDENTS TO A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE THROUGH FITNESS-YOGA

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Abstract. *This scientific article focuses on the results of the analysis of modern research in the field of healthy lifestyle development, the analysis of several models of health care today, their effective influence and understanding of the role and place of health care in human life and activities.*

Keywords: *model, healthy lifestyle, fitness, yoga, health, development.*

Development and implementation of a healthy lifestyle development model that allows for the implementation of measures aimed at the health care and strengthening of the higher education system in order to effectively solve the problems of developing a healthy lifestyle among students in the educational space of the university need to increase.

Modeling (latin “modulus”) is a measurement, standard, image or sample of a system of objects. Knowledge allows researching objects, making models of existing objects and events, and systematic learning. The modeling method is widely used in modern science, it facilitates the process of scientific research, and in some cases, it becomes the only means of studying complex objects. This is especially important in the study of abstract objects and the educational process. Models are used to explain the properties of an object and the processes that occur in it.

Modeling of pedagogical conditions for the development of a healthy lifestyle is included in the researches of R.A.Qasimov [14], T.V.Klimova [15], M.O.Shuaybovoy [24], J.F.Jimenez-Parra [2], N.V.Tretyakova [5], N.E.Kasatkina [13] and others. Currently, several models of healthy lifestyle development are presented in foreign studies.

The medical-prophylactic model (A. Charlton, W. Blair [1]) is based on informing people about the behaviors and factors that affect health. This model is often called cognitive. The authors of the model argue that the most important condition for a healthy lifestyle is to inform a person about the health risks of a certain behavior or the benefits of certain behaviors aimed at maintaining health. According to critics of this model, this view is simplistic of the problem of health care and health behavior development. The reason is that not only informational factors are involved in the mechanism of human behavior.

The radical-political model was developed by E.Rogers and F.Shoumaker [3] and helps a person to make a decision to lead a healthy lifestyle by changing external conditions (legislation, social conditions, etc.) based on the idea that it is possible to create a living environment that provides.

The most universal and practice-oriented model, which takes into account a number of factors affecting human behavior aimed at maintaining health, is the health action model developed by the English scientist K.Tones [4]. Such a model is capable of combining the entire spectrum of social and psychological influences that a person faces. The content of this model combines, first of all, activities for health, as well as factors affecting such activities, including human behavior, his value system and motivation. Actions for the benefit of health are carried out on the basis of

information that must be perceived by a person at an interdisciplinary level. A necessary aspect of the model is general social norms.

In our opinion, in order to effectively solve the issues of developing a healthy lifestyle among students in the educational field of the university, it is necessary to introduce a model aimed at the implementation of a set of pedagogical conditions aimed at maintaining and strengthening health into the educational system.

This model consists of three interconnected blocks: *theoretical, content-activity and evaluative-resultative*. They help to understand the essence of the studied object in more depth and detail.

The *theoretical* block of the model contains a description of methodological approaches and principles of developing a healthy lifestyle for students. This block summarizes the principles of *systematic, person-centered, activity-based, and competency-based* approaches. All approaches complement each other, the integration of approaches determines the choice of actions to implement the model.

The *systematic approach* in pedagogy implies an approach to the pedagogical process as a system - a set of clearly structured and closely interconnected elements. This approach, unlike the traditional subject approach, is more qualitative and modern. One of the founders of the systematic approach is K.L.Bertalanfi [6].

It is impossible to create and design a healthcare environment in an educational institution without implementing a systematic approach. A systematic approach to the organization of health care activities in an educational institution is related to the need for a deep, multi-level and multifaceted analysis of the educational process and its impact on human health. A systematic approach to the development of a healthy lifestyle allows you to select and carefully study each element of the system, analyze and compare them by combining them into a coherent structure. At the same time, all their similarities and differences, contradictions and connecting features, the priority of some elements over others, the dynamics of development of each element and the whole system are determined.

Person-oriented approach appeared within humanistic psychology A.Maslow, K.Rogers, [7], I.S.Yakimanskaya [25] and others played an important role in the development of general scientific principles as methodological bases of this approach. Developing a healthy lifestyle of students in person-centered education, creating an appropriate health-saving educational environment and allowing students to directly study independently and without intermediaries, make independent decisions characterized by the implementation of a comprehensive system of enabling conditions. A person-oriented approach in the field of health care has an educational, developmental and formative character that affects the student's personality. This approach to the fitness tool allows to combine personal and practical components and develop the main concept – “personally oriented fitness tool” is the process of developing healthy lifestyle social skills, civic attitudes, behavioral culture among students. In order to implement a person-oriented fitness tool, it is necessary to understand the health-related components of health-related fitness, healthy lifestyle values, development of social activity, as well as self-improvement of motor skills and physical abilities. The main characteristic of students who choose types of physical activity is their personal motivation. The choice of the type of activity with the help of fitness is the student's awareness of his decision, and in making such a choice, the principle of democratization and humanization implemented during the joint activity of the student and the teacher can be

maximally used. For the effective cooperation of the student and the teacher in this type of activity, programs and instructions are drawn up, and practical complexes of fitness exercises are developed for students. The concretization of fitness technologies aimed at meeting the needs and motivations of the student in the selected type of physical activity is of particular importance in the process of implementing a person-oriented approach. Implementation of such technologies in practical activities helps to develop new original forms of physical culture.

The main positions of the *active approach* were formed by L.S.Vygotsky [8], A.A.Leontiev [18], S.L.Rubinshtein [12] and others. In the most general form, an active approach means organizing and managing the student's health care activities in the general context of his life. At the same time, the activity approach implemented in the life context of a specific person, taking into account his life plans, value orientations and other parameters of the subjective world, is essentially a personal-activity approach. It is carried out by creating conditions for strengthening theoretical knowledge in the field of health care based on practical activities. From the point of view of an active approach, the essence of the development of a healthy lifestyle is to focus on the joint activities of the teacher and the student aimed at achieving the goals and tasks of health care. The student not only perceives ready-made knowledge, but also participates in the process of self-improvement. In this case, personally important motives that stimulate activity are activated.

In real conditions, a healthy lifestyle can be effectively implemented using the comprehensive potential of its educational and educational nature, that is, based on the active approach of fitness. The student acquires a system of certain scientific knowledge and practical skills important for a healthy lifestyle, forms a worldview focused on the value of health care, and develops the necessary physical abilities.

The concept of a *competence-based approach* has become widespread relatively recently in connection with the signing of the Bologna Declaration at the Berlin Conference in 2003. Competency-based approach was the result of new requirements for the quality of education [10]. Currently, major scientific-theoretical and scientific-methodological works have already appeared, in which the essence of the competency-based approach and the problems of developing basic competencies are highlighted in the works of most researchers. (R.K.Gilmeeva [9], I.A.Zimina [11], E.V.Kondratenko [17], V.A.Slastenina [21], A.V.Khutorsky, A.A.Sharapov [23]).

The implementation of methodological approaches in the process of developing a healthy lifestyle of students includes the organization of an educational environment that preserves health, taking into account the following general didactic principles (*systematic, scientific, individualization and differential principles*). The principles that reflect the specific features of the development of a healthy lifestyle of students with the help of fitness technologies include *flexibility (adaptive), loadability, psychological regulation, openness and adequacy of choice, aesthetic suitability, adaptation to the student contingent, control and monitoring of students' physical condition, principles* such as *hedonism* and *the stimulation of interest* were developed and based on the research of E.G.Saykina [20].

Among the many principles proposed by E.G.Saykina, we single out five specific principles based on the biological, pedagogical and psychological laws of health training development and reflecting the laws of functioning of such a complex, multifunctional socio-cultural phenomenon as fitness. we considered it appropriate to show.

The principle of *loadability* is one of the most important principles of fitness. The principle of loadability reflects the general ideology of fitness, the goal of which is to maintain the body in the

most optimal physiological state. This principle implies the absence of competitive motives and aspirations to achieve a high sports result, which defines the specific characteristics of all fitness programs. The principle of loadability should not be understood as reducing the load to a minimum level, because it is impossible to increase and even maintain the level of psychophysical potential without physical strength. It should also be noted that physical activity during fitness training should not be high, such training should have a healthy character and correct the physical development of the participants, as well as increase their physical fitness.

The principle of *adequacy* of fitness includes the selection of optimal means and methods for achieving a specific goal, based on the individual characteristics of people engaged in physical activity. Each student has the right to choose one or another type of fitness, it depends only on the student's interest and motivation to engage in this type of physical activity.

The principle of *aesthetic expediency* is one of the first principles developed in fitness. In addition to the task of improving health, the appearance of a serious stimulus and motivation in fitness participants satisfies the aesthetic needs of a person (beautiful body shape, correct height, etc.). Fitness training awakens the desire to achieve beauty in a person's appearance, shapes the beauty of actions, teaches to see the beauty around, relationships between people.

The principle of *psychological regulation* determines the need to reduce the level of anxiety and stress of those involved through fitness exercises that allow to relieve muscle tension and regulate the state of the nervous system. A special selection of musical accompaniment will help this: from high-impact music therapy to low-impact, for example, autogenic training.

The principle of *control and monitoring* of the physical condition of those engaged in fitness is planning and optimal regulation of physical activity based on the individual capabilities of the student's physical and functional fitness. Such monitoring is carried out in the form of a test in order to determine the desired health effect from the chosen fitness direction and to achieve the maximum positive result and to make additional adjustments to the fitness program.

We used the above principles as a basis for developing a model for developing a healthy lifestyle of students with the help of fitness technologies. The goal of the considered model is to develop a healthy lifestyle of students with the help of fitness technologies. Achieving this goal can be done by solving problems that correspond to the specific stages of development of this type of activity of students, taking into account the opportunities provided by fitness technologies:

- to develop students' awareness of the value of a healthy lifestyle and interest in fitness technologies;
- acquiring knowledge about the essence of healthy lifestyle and fitness technologies;
- use of fitness technologies in the design and organization of health care activities;
- develop the ability to assess the impact of fitness technologies on human health, analyze the results of health care activities, identify errors and shortcomings for further correction of actions.

The analysis of the educational programs carried out within the framework of our research shows that the subjects “Valeology”, “Physical culture” and “Safety of life activities” play an important role in the development of general cultural and universal competences related to health care. These disciplines build competencies in physical and mental health. Currently, in the educational environment of many universities, these subjects have been removed from the catalog of subjects in the curriculum. This, in turn, requires a different approach to the development of a healthy lifestyle for students.

Therefore, we divided the *content-activity* block of the process of developing a healthy lifestyle of students into the main (invariant) part and variable (variant) components through the didactic possibilities of general professional subjects in the curriculum. The main (invariant) component is implemented through auditorium activities, and the variable component is implemented through non-auditorium activities.

The variable component of the development of a healthy lifestyle of students includes the introduction of fitness technologies in the course of extracurricular activities of students based on mobile applications, media, social networks and student associations (fitness clubs, departments, network communities). , which allows you to combine practical training in selected types of fitness with basic rational nutrition advice. The purpose of studying fitness technologies for students is to master the methodology of training in various fields of fitness, to develop the correct posture during training, to strengthen skeletal muscles and improve the mobility of internal organs, to strengthen health and a healthy body. is to acquire lifestyle skills. Fitness technologies are focused on all types of physical activity and include sets of physical exercises: strength training, aerobic, anaerobic, fitness-yoga, etc.

In the studies devoted to the problems of developing a healthy lifestyle among university students, it was noted that the organization of *physical culture* or other wellness activities in universities using outdated organizational forms and methods is not effective and does not give the desired results. According to the experts' conclusion, with this approach to the organization of *physical culture* training aimed at solving the problems reflected by the indicators of physical fitness and the standards of the credit module of the curriculum, the attitude of students to health and lifestyle always improves. Also, the analysis of educational and regulatory documents shows that the science of *physical culture* has been removed from the curriculum of most pedagogical higher education institutions (bachelor's field is not physical culture).

Taking into account the appearance of the term “fitness technologies” and its specific features, it should be said that these technologies are developed in accordance with the goals and objectives of fitness, based on its principles, which take into account the motivation of the participants, their age and physiological characteristics and others are considered.

The structure of fitness technologies can be distinguished according to the following directions: aerobic programs (Step-aerobics); strength directions of fitness (CrossFit, Tabata); mixed format programs; low-intensity "Mind Body" programs (fitness-yoga, stretching); dance programs (Zumba, hip-hop) and digital technologies used in fitness (mobile applications, social networks, online platforms) [16]. All of them are aimed at improving the health of the body: a person is aware of his functional state, follows the rules of rational nutrition, leads a healthy lifestyle by increasing muscle mass, reducing fat balance, improving the functional and physical fitness of the body. In the framework of educational organizations of foreign countries, as a rule, fitness is carried out in the form of group training to maintain physical fitness and improve sports. Regardless of the type of fitness, the algorithm for implementing fitness technologies has the following stages: first, the development and approval of a short-term and long-term program; secondly, making an agreement with the executor of the developed program, which will allow you to achieve the desired result on time and make physical activity a necessary component of life; thirdly, current, operational and step-by-step control of the condition of those involved in the implementation of the program to analyze the reactions of the body to physical activity; fourthly,

based on the analysis of the results obtained from the conducted training, the effectiveness of the used fitness program is evaluated and its further correction is carried out.

The development of a model for the development of a healthy lifestyle of students is a systematic process, in which the main idea is to prepare students for independent management of a healthy lifestyle and to use general didactic technologies and activity-type technologies (fitness technologies) in future health activities. is to implement a healthy lifestyle. As a result of mastering fitness technologies, the student knows the complex control methods and organization of fitness classes, can use practical forms, methods and tools of fitness technologies in interaction with the subjects of the educational process; be able to shape your own physical activity and healthy lifestyle based on the needs for physical training; learns how to make a habit of the components of a healthy lifestyle using fitness technologies, to identify mistakes in performing exercises and to find ways to eliminate them in the process of mastering new types of exercises.

Pedagogical monitoring is an effective tool that allows evaluating the effectiveness of developing a healthy lifestyle of students. Pedagogical monitoring includes a system of collecting, storing, processing, evaluating, analyzing, predicting and distributing information about the pedagogical process. Pedagogical monitoring is an element of the evaluation and effective block of the considered model, which allows to assess the impact of fitness technologies on human health.

Monitoring of the development of a healthy lifestyle of students performs several functions at the same time: diagnostics that evaluates and analyzes the results of health care activities; control reveals the management function that allows to correct and predict the errors and shortcomings in the development of this type of training and the state of the healthcare process.

The implementation of the model includes the monitoring of the development of a healthy lifestyle of students using fitness technologies. Pedagogical monitoring at the initial work stage includes diagnosing the level of development of healthy lifestyle of students.

Diagnostics can be carried out using A.G.Nosov's "development of healthy lifestyle components in students" [19], S.Deryabo and V.Yasvin's "health care attitude index" and other methods. This allows us to evaluate the motivational-valuable, cognitive, active-creative and evaluative-reflexive criteria of developing a healthy lifestyle as a diagnostic tool [26].

The identifying and summarizing stage of experimental work includes diagnostic methods aimed at studying the motivation of students to maintain and strengthen their health, determining the level of basic knowledge about communicative and organizational trends, and the ability to reflect. A pedagogical test (interview, questionnaire) will be conducted to determine the level of knowledge of the basics of a healthy lifestyle.

The analysis of the results of the student's health care activities determines the level of readiness of students to practice a healthy lifestyle.

The evaluative-effective block of the model is presented in the form of motivational-valuable, cognitive, active-creative and evaluative-reflexive criteria for indicators describing students' readiness to manage and implement a healthy lifestyle, the level of formation of this preparation.

Thus, all considered components of the model of development of a healthy lifestyle of students act as a single system. Each component of the model is responsible for solving a specific problem, so the unity of all components ensures the achievement of a common goal.

Pedagogical conditions for the effective implementation of this model include the introduction of fitness technologies into the health-preserving educational environment of the university; use of didactic possibilities (potential) of basic academic subjects in the process of preparing students for a healthy lifestyle; involving students in practical activities independently (outside the auditorium) on the implementation of a healthy lifestyle; consists of monitoring students' readiness for a healthy lifestyle.

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